

DEVELOPMENT OF A 15 METRE DIAMETER HIGH PERFORMANCE, LOW COST RADIO ANTENNA FOR THE SQUARE KILOMETRE ARRAY

Gordon Lacy, P.Eng¹

¹National Research Council, DRAO, PO Box 248 Penticton, BC, Canada, V2A-6J9
Email: gordon.lacy@nrc.ca, web page: <http://www.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/eng/solutions/facilities/drao.html>

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ABSTRACT

The specifications for the radio reflector telescopes required for the Square Kilometer Array (SKA) project are particularly challenging and unique. The SKA project is an international project with the aim to build the world's largest radio telescope array. Very high performance is required, but the dishes must also meet strict cost targets. At the same time a large number of dishes needs to be fabricated (~2000) in a relatively short time, and a very low variation between reflectors is desirable. It was felt that a conventional approach had little chance of meeting both the cost and performance targets, so a novel approach was adopted. The choice of the 15m aperture offset Gregorian optics design was made by the SKA project office. This paper will focus on the structural design and fabrication of the Canadian DVA-1 (Dish Verification Antenna-1) prototype which has achieved a surface accuracy of 0.89mm RMS (unweighted).

Figure 1: SKA prototype radio telescope, complete and undergoing tests.

The design adopted deviates widely from current radio telescope design practice. The primary reflector (15m x 18.2m) is a thin (5.3mm), rim supported carbon composite shell molded in a single piece using vacuum infusion technology. The secondary, a 4m elliptical thin carbon shell supported at just 4 points on the rim, was also fabricated in a single piece using vacuum infusion. The backup structure behind the main reflector is built up from steel tubes. Unusually, the reflector surface is used to transmit structural loads and a semi-compliant connection at the reflector center is employed to minimize distortions in the reflector surface. Several types of optimization were undertaken to develop the structure.

Attaining the required stiffness of the feed and secondary support structure was also challenging. Free-shape topology optimization was used to explore different design directions, which ultimately led to the radically different carbon tube structure shown in the images.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite radio telescope development has been ongoing at the Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory (DRAO) since 2005. This development has culminated in the design and construction of the latest telescope, the subject of this paper, the DVA-1. The complete design involved a team of people, and included the design of the optics, the mount pedestal and drive components and other parts of this complex system. This paper will concentrate only on the composite structures.

2 DESIGN

2.1 Design Requirements, Reflector Surface

The radio reflector surface must satisfy a host of (often conflicting) requirements. The surface must be very dimensionally stable, yet inexpensive. It must be highly radio reflective. It should have a high specific stiffness, be UV stable, and have a very precisely defined shape. It must be fatigue resistant, and not suffer from corrosion or other weathering effects. Traditional radio telescopes almost universally use non-structural machined aluminium panels mounted on a steel space frame backing structure. Carbon composite material offers a higher thermal stability through a lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), along with a much higher specific stiffness than aluminium. Composite construction also offers the possibility to mold much larger panels in an inexpensive and repeatable way. The DVA-1 carries this idea to the logical extreme, molding the entire reflector surface as a single piece. This has the advantage of eliminating all of the panel gaps and panel edges (both of which degrade the performance). Molding in one piece also reduces PID (Process Induced Distortion) through the locking in of some of the internal stresses. Clearly there are many other challenges (and uncertainties) to overcome, including PID, radio reflectivity, weathering etc. In addition, molding the primary reflector in one piece means building on-site or near-site unless the reflector is rather small (about 6m in diameter or less). On the DVA-1 these challenges have been overcome, or (in the case of some of the concerns) are being actively studied.

2.2 Design, Reflector Structure

Many factors led us to the development of a rim supported, single skin (uncored), carbon reflector. Cored structures were tried on earlier designs, but even though cored structures offer several advantages such as greatly increased local bending stiffness and ease of fabrication using vacuum infusion (with core surface grooves), other aspects of the cored structure were not so desirable. The undesirable aspects include high thermal resistance, increased PID, and the added material and installation costs associated with core. From a telescope performance point of view the high thermal resistance is detrimental. On a clear night, with high emissivity paint, the side of the reflector facing the sky will radiate to the cold sky and drop its temperature 3 to 4 degrees below ambient. The backside will remain at ambient, with the net effect being a distortion of the cored structure because the cold side has shrunk. The opposite effect occurs during the day when the sun heats up one side leaving the other side near ambient. Low CTE materials help but do not eliminate this effect. Thin solid carbon structures (painted white to control internal temperatures) have sufficiently high thermal conductivity to render this problem insignificant.

Rim supported concave reflectors are also very stable in wind. Earlier designs with directly bonded-on beams must generate bending stiffness in the reflector surface between the beams in order to avoid gravitational and wind induced deflections. The rim supported beamless monocoque structure does not have these local stiffness 'hard spots' in its surface and therefore remains very smooth under wind and gravity loads (see Figure 1).

Another aspect of the DVA-1 design is the incorporation of a semi-compliant connector at the centre of the primary reflector [1]. This is a clever feature that allows the primary reflector to act as a load bearing part of the structure at low elevation angles, yet when the primary rim is horizontal, vertical deflection (sag) of the backing structure at the rim does not cause a bump in the centre of the reflector, which it would if the connection was not allowed movement in this direction. The use of fibreglass for the construction of this 'diaphragm spring' is ideal because of its high strength but low modulus.

2.3 Design, Primary Reflector Rim.

The primary reflector is supported at 9 points around the rim on 13 tubular steel struts (some support points have two struts). The rim is stiffened using carbon composite backing pieces which are bonded on separately (see Figure 2a). The connections to the struts are accomplished using a vacuum infused carbon fibre upper part together with a compression molded lower piece and a captured steel ball stud for the final connection to the strut (Figure 2b). This design prevents the transfer of moments from the back structure to the dish surface. This design of carbon composite reflector surface mounted on steel struts allows the dissimilar thermal expansion rates of the carbon composite and steel to move without distorting the reflector surface. Figure 2 shows the general arrangement.

Figure 2a: Bonded on composite rim stiffeners, 2b: connection between support struts and dish rim.

3 PROCESS INDUCED DISTORTION

Process induced distortion (PID) is also of major concern. A great deal was learned about PID in relation to radio telescopes in the past 10 years. Contracts were let to [2] to study this problem and the results were used in the design of the DVA-1. The choice of structural materials for the DVA-1 dish was driven to a large extent by the PID requirements. The principle contributors to PID are (in the order of importance):

1. The resin absorption layer on the surface of the structural core.
2. The use of unidirectional fabrics in the structure
3. Changes in total thickness of the laminate
4. Anisotropy of fabric properties

For these reasons the structure of the DVA-1 went through considerable metamorphosis. The most radical was the elimination of the structural core. Because the dish surface is a tension structure supported by the outer rim, the core is not required for the fundamental structural loads, but was useful for mitigating local bending stresses induced by some remaining moment loads and also for buckling induced by 'backside' winds.

The reason why structural foam core should contribute so much to PID was not at all clear to the author but perhaps the mechanism can be understood if the resin layer on the surface of the core is considered as adding to the resin ratio of the laminate on each side of the sandwich. This, of course, has the effect of increasing the cure shrinkage of the laminate, which leads to greater PID. The mechanism of PID with the Unidirectional is probably self evident; the material is highly anisotropic, so distortions perpendicular to the fibres are resin dominated while along the fibre length shrinkage is fibre dominated. Effect number three, caused by changes in structural thickness, are less self-evident, but definitely real. The solution for this problem was to post-bond any large structural thickness change. For the DVA-1, this meant post-bonding a reinforced circular patch at the dish center where the diaphragm connector attaches to the back of the primary reflector. For item four, anisotropy of fabric properties, every attempt was made to both 'smear out' any potential anisotropy through careful

design of the layup, and also to use the most isotropic fabric available. For the latter, a braided triaxial fabric from A&P Technologies was chosen [3]. This fabric has the unique property of combining three fibre directions into a single woven (braided) structure in a fully balanced fashion. Not only is the material orthotropic in the usual planer sense, but the three fibre directions ($0, \pm 60$), are interwoven so that no 'Z' offset exists between fibre directions as would be typical with a prepreg structure made from unidirectionals or a structure made from multiple layers of $0-90$ and ± 45 fabric. Additionally, an orthotropic structure can be created with fewer layers of material and without strict adherence to through-thickness symmetry (necessary to avoid potato-chipping distortions in the typical prepreg-from-uni type of structure). Also because only three fibre directions are needed instead of 4 ($0, \pm 45, 90$), a higher stiffness can be reached in the fibre directions (albeit with slightly higher stiffness 'troughs' between fibre directions). A side benefit of using braided material is the extreme toughness of the structure. This was demonstrated when the primary reflector was damaged during transport via helicopter. The reflector was essentially turned inside out during the flight. This damage would have been catastrophic for a thin metal reflector, but, although there were 21 tears in the structure that had to be repaired, the reflector was repaired, and the dish still met specifications. It was clear from this accident that the dish, except for local damage around the 21 tears, retained its elasticity, and 'popped' back into its original shape.

4 OPTIMIZATION

Structural optimization methods were employed on the primary reflector backing structure and on the secondary and feed support structures. The work was carried out under contract with [4]. Optimization work started with full 3-D topological studies. These studies lead to a confirmation of some of the early concepts and a radical redesign of other parts of the structure. Once the new more-optimal shape was established, further optimizations were carried out by allowing laminate thicknesses, tube diameters and tube wall thicknesses to vary. Figure 3 shows the result of this work. The feed and secondary support structures (structure above the green primary), were particularly

Figure 3: 3-D topological optimization result left, final DVA-1 design on right

interesting in that they were completely different than the conventional ladder-type support structures employed on every other offset reflector built to date. One of the principle difficulties with an offset design is in attaining sufficient stiffness in the structure to retain good optical alignment of the reflecting surfaces. Structural optimization gives us the tools to find this optimal solution while also keeping costs low.

5 ANALYSIS

The primary design driver for radio telescopes is deflection of the optical surfaces (and focal point). Every effort is needed to ensure the perfect rigidity of these structures. Since this is impossible, the nearest approximation to perfect rigidity is required with the added proviso that this rigidity is not acquired at too high of an expense. The alternative, the inclusion of some active elements, has been employed in a very few radio telescopes, but was not considered here due to the added complexity and

the concern over long term reliability and cost. Structural analysis performed on this telescope includes the usual set of static FEA, normal modes, and buckling. Wind loads were determined by a set of wind tunnel tests run at NRC-IAR [5]. NeiNastran [6] was used for the analysis. Optimized mesh models received from Altair [4] could be directly imported into NeiNastran and verified before further work was carried out in-house (a decided advantage). Additional (manual) iterations on the structure were also carried out using NeiNastran.

6 FABRICATION

6.1 The fabrication process

The only process seriously considered for the fabrication of the composite structures on the DVA-1 was vacuum infusion. Hand-layup was not considered for several reasons which included higher shrinkage, lower part consistency, lower specific strength and stiffness, and higher weight. On the other end of the scale, pre-preg was not chosen because of its higher cost and the non-availability of an autoclave large enough to house the complete reflector. More exploration into room temperature cure prepregs could still be done, but the overall process is still likely to be more expensive due to increased material cost, increased labour, increased number of steps, and increased use of disposable materials.

The principle limitation on the size of a vacuum infused part is the height. There are no real limitations on the horizontal extent of the part that cannot be overcome with a careful infusion strategy (together with some computer modeling). In the vertical extent one is limited by atmospheric pressure, because it is the motive force by which the resin is forced into the part. This would indicate that the tallest parts are best made at sea level (or even better, under water!). The author has previously made one part that was over 6m tall and 55m long, which is close to the practical limit. Larger parts have been made since, but not taller parts. That being said, infusing a single piece radio reflector about 18m long x 15m wide x 2m tall does not present any new challenges in terms of horizontal extent or height.

6.2 Vacuum Infusion Design

As a large infusion the radio reflector part does present some unique challenges. At first it appears as a very simple dish-shaped object that should be easy enough to infuse, but there are three principle difficulties. First, it is very wide compared to a boat hull or wind blade which introduces one difficulty. Second, and most importantly, the mold is convex, not concave. It is very convenient for the exhausting of air during the part filling process, and for the escape of gasses during the curing stage, if the highest point on the part is also the last to fill, and that this point is on the outer edge of the part. Since the typical radio dish mold is convex, not concave, an alternate method to fill the part had to be arranged. Figure 4b shows the manifold design used on the DVA-1 secondary. This is also, with minor variations, the same manifold design that the author has used on the last 5 reflectors he has built. The idea is to fill from several points around the main manifold 'ring' (rectangle near top of Figure 4). The filling pattern can be seen in Figure 4a. The part fills simultaneously outwards and downwards on the outer side of the manifold ring, and inwards and upwards on the inner side. The trick, which requires some flow modeling [6], is to get the two fill rates to be about equal so that the resin front reaches all parts of the outer (lower) rim vacuum and the top vacuums at the same time. In fact it is best if the top vacuums fill last, since it is these vacuum lines that should remain open and drawing vacuum all the way until the part cures. In reality there shouldn't be much of a difference in filling times between the two flow fronts, because there is never enough safety margin between the resin gel time and the fill time to allow much of a delta between any two flow fronts. In practical terms one sets the gel time at 3x the fill time during the modeling stage, but this comfortable margin is easily eroded through variations in shop temperature, humidity, resin chemistry, and the typical non-ideal reality of the flow in the real manifold and real laminate.

Figure 4a: later stages of resin infusion of the DVA-1 4m secondary showing filling of top area last, 4b: manifold layout showing radial lines emanating from square shaped primary manifold near top

The third difficulty is in the nature of filling carbon fibre parts. Carbon is difficult to wet-out. Adding to this is the need to have a high fibre content part with a high degree of fidelity to the mold shape. This requirement precludes the use of embedded lower fibre ratio layers within the part. It also disallows the trick of adding flow mesh between the mold surface and the part. So instead we are left with a low permeability part that must be wet-out slowly with a low (carefully matched) permeability flow medium. As a vacuum infusion practitioner I can only lament the lack of availability of a sufficient selection of lower permeability flow mediums for these tough to infuse carbon layups. Alternatively, a nice thin Vinylester resin which didn't also have an unacceptably high shrinkage would be wonderful. The process is one of balancing all the requirements and ultimately ending up with the best compromise between strength, shrinkage, and flow rate.

7 HELICOPTER TRANSPORT AND ACCIDENT

The primary reflector was fabricated in a leased building several kilometers from the site where it was to be mounted to its support structure. This was done simply because no building was available on-site that would accommodate the 15m x 18.2m reflector. Due to the size of this part, and in particular its width, the only option for transport was by helicopter. Being made from composite, the primary reflector weight was about three metric tonnes which was well within the capability of the helicopter. Initially all went as planned; the helicopter lifted the payload and carried it off over the mountain that separated the fabrication facility from the installation site. Unfortunately there was an incident that occurred just before the dish was to be set down at its destination. Whether due to a wind gust or pilot error is uncertain, but the reflector, exacerbated by its large area and light weight, flipped up from the horizontal position in which it was being transported to a near vertical position and then dropped back down again. The initial 'flip up' did not cause any damage, but the very large thin membrane that constitutes this structure buckled when the dish came back down because of the high deceleration as it came up against the hard stop of the forward support lines. The dish was delivered moments later, but in a decidedly crumpled state (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The DVA-1 reflector as delivered by helicopter to its assembly site.

8 REPAIR

In some ways the accident was a blessing in disguise. There are plenty of people in the world that are still distrustful of composites and one of the questions that gets asked is “how can we repair it”? The very satisfactory recovery from almost total disaster began with the use of large air-bag lift devices normally employed for righting trucks that have been involved in accidents. This was accomplished just 3 days after the incident and resulted in the dish being popped back out to its original shape. Local damage was sustained of course, and there were 21 tears in the surface ranging from about 0.3m in length up to 6m long which had to be repaired. This work was performed where the dish sat as seen in Figure 5. A temporary air-supported enclosure was constructed using polyethylene, a low pressure fan, and a fairly large outdoor diesel heater, necessary because the work was done from October into November and the outside temperatures were dropping down to as low as -15C at night. All repairs were done using vacuum infusion. All repairs required structural reconstruction on the outside (convex) side of the part, and surface repairs on the inside (concave, reflector) side of the part. All repairs also required laser tracking and shoring to restore the local shape due to the loss of structural integrity in the area immediately adjacent to the damage. Figure 6a shows the typical shoring of the damaged areas underneath the dish, while figure 6b shows the infusion of one of the largest damaged areas.

Figure 6a: Repairing the DVA-1 local shoring under damage, 6b: infusion of the largest crack

The repair scenario involved first grinding the structure back on either side of the break in a long (150mm) scarph. The scarph grind went from nothing at the backside surface 150mm from the break

down to the first layer of laminate at the break. Replacement laminates were cut to fit into this scarphed area with some overlap, starting with narrow pieces and staggering out to the full width of the scarph plus an additional 25mm of overlap on each side. The top (backside) layer overlaps the top layer of the part, providing the same total thickness of laminate as the original part, remembering that the first layer of the scarph joint sits on top of the first layer of the original structure (nearest the inside of the part).

9 MEASUREMENT AND TESTING

A laser tracker was used for all measurements both for setting up the shoring for the repaired areas and later for measuring the dish surface. The Faro laser tracker (see reference [8]), has a maximum precision of about 15 microns, which is just fine for the current application. Once the dish was repaired it was mounted on its steel backing structure and measured several times. Figure 7 shows the results of one of these measurements. The damaged areas clearly show up as (most) of the red areas.

Figure 7a: repaired areas as white hatched lines, 7b: dish on backing structure

The RMS (Root Mean Square) error of the repaired surface was 0.89mm. Considering that the original design target was <math><1\text{mm}</math> it is clear that despite the accident we were still able to meet specifications. Figure 7b also shows structure that is in the mold itself. The 4 horizontal bands for instance are the edges of the 5 mold pieces. The grid pattern seen at about the 2 o'clock position is also in the mold, a result of the underlying grid structure of the mold surface.

Other mechanical tests included vibration analysis using dropped weights. This series of tests has given us information on the actual normal modes in the structure as well as uncovering one problem of a loose connection between a backside strut and one of the spherical joints used to isolate moments between the backside struts and the composite dish surface. Radio holography has also been performed. This technique can be used to map the radio reflective surface. This has been done, along with comparisons with the physical surface measurements, the result being that the two surfaces are identical within the measurement tolerances.

10 CONCLUSIONS

The DVA-1 telescope easily meets its original design goals despite the unfortunate helicopter incident and the subsequent damage to the primary reflector. Fabricating a single piece radio telescope primary reflector of this size is quite feasible and has been demonstrated. Repairing this same reflector after the near catastrophic helicopter incident was performed under a simple polyethylene bubble 'tent' in winter conditions, demonstrating that composite materials are repairable even under marginal conditions. I also believe that this accident (a blessing in disguise), demonstrates the robustness of composites and should remove any doubt that a single piece reflector of this size need be considered a liability. It is hard to imagine what sort of catastrophic event would lead to the unrepairable loss of the whole reflector.

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